

LOW-ENERGY ELECTRON MULTIPLICATION ON NANOSTRUCTURED SOLAR CELLS: A NOVEL ROUTE TO OVERCOME SI-PV EFFICIENCY LIMITS

Mikaël Hosatte¹, Brice Rouffie¹, Zbigniew T. Kuznicki¹, Frédéric Milési², Bertrand Paviet-Salomon³, Audrey Morisset³, Philippe Wyss³, Lejo J. Koduvelikulathu⁴, Lazhar Rachdi⁴, Lacramioara Popescu⁴, Dominik Rudolph⁴, Marek Basta⁵, Andrzej Miszczuk⁵, Martyna Majak⁵, Beata Basta⁵, Samuel Queste⁶

Corresponding author: mikaël.hosatte@segton.com

¹ Segton Advanced Technology, 99 Boulevard de la Reine, Versailles 78000, France

² CEA-Leti, 17 avenue de Martyrs, 38054 Grenoble, France

³ CSEM, Rue Jaquet-Droz 1, 2002 Neuchâtel, Switzerland

⁴ ISC Konstanz e.V., Rudolf-Diesel-Straße 15, 78467 Konstanz, Germany

⁵ Roltec, Swiety Marcin 29/8, Poznan 61-806, Poland

⁶ Marie and Louis Pasteur University, 1 Rue Claude Goudimel, 25000 Besançon, France

ABSTRACT: Silicon photovoltaics, while dominating global photovoltaic production, are approaching the Shockley–Queisser efficiency limit. The LEEMONS project, funded by Horizon Europe (Grant 101172870), develops a novel nanostructured solar cell concept based on Low-Energy Electron Multiplication (LEEM). This process enables a single high-energy photon to generate multiple low-energy electrons, thereby reducing thermalisation losses and increasing photocurrent. The consortium integrates advanced ion implantation, annealing and metallisation techniques to demonstrate proof-of-concept prototypes using industrially relevant solar technologies such as heterojunction cells. Early results confirm the fabrication of ion-implanted nanostructured layers, validation of implantation masks and low-temperature metallisation alternatives. LEEMONS offers a scalable, industry-compatible pathway to higher Si-PV efficiencies, with strong alignment to EU goals on renewable energy, climate neutrality and technological sovereignty. **Keywords:** Photovoltaics, electron multiplication, nanostructures, ion implantation, silicon solar cells

1 INTRODUCTION AND CONCEPT

Silicon photovoltaics have experienced remarkable cost reductions and global expansion over the past two decades. However, conventional Si solar cells remain constrained by the Shockley–Queisser limit [1]. As a result, further efficiency improvements through incremental advances are limited and new physical concepts are needed to sustain both performance gains and continued cost reductions.

The LEEMONS project (Low-Energy Electron Multiplication on Nanostructured Solar Cells) investigates a novel approach to carrier generation in nanostructured silicon. It is based on the concept of Low-Energy Electron Multiplication (LEEM), where high-energy photons generate multiple low-energy electrons instead of dissipating their excess energy through thermalisation. Nanostructuring is achieved through ion implantation, which locally amorphises the silicon, followed by specialised annealing that induces partial recrystallisation and interface flattening. This process reorganises atoms at the amorphous/crystalline (a-Si/c-Si) interfaces, enhancing electron multiplication through modifications of the electronic energy levels. This mechanism reduces thermalisation losses and enhances photocurrent, offering a disruptive pathway for efficiency improvements in silicon photovoltaics (Si-PV).

In contrast to tandem architectures, LEEM does not rely on new absorber materials and remains fully compatible with established silicon technology. Its scalable fabrication relies on industrial processes such as ion implantation, annealing and passivation, which are already widespread in semiconductor manufacturing.

2 ORGANISATION AND OBJECTIVES

LEEMONS (Project 101172870, Horizon Europe) is a 36-month RIA action running from November 2024 to October 2027. The consortium gathers six European partners across the value chain:

- **Segton Advanced Technology (Coordinator)** – development of the LEEM concept, communication and project management
- **CEA-Leti** – development of ion implantation and annealing processes
- **ISC Konstanz** – integration of LEEM layers into c-Si solar cells and optimisation
- **CSEM** – adaptation to back-contact solar cell architectures and characterisation
- **Roltec** – development of metallisation alternatives, lifetime studies, characterisation and simulation
- **Marie and Louis Pasteur University** – fabrication of silicon masks by Deep Reactive Ion Etching (RIE)

Figure 1: Overview of the LEEMONS partners.

Objectives:

1. Prototype a game-changing photovoltaic innovation through nanotechnology
2. Demonstrate lab-scale proof-of-concept devices on PERC and HJT cells.
3. Ensure high compatibility with industrial Si PV lines (80–95%).
4. Deliver cost-effective, sustainable solutions aligned with EU climate neutrality and strategic autonomy

3 TECHNOLOGY

The LEEMONS technology builds on the principle of LEEM in ion-implanted nanostructures embedded in crystalline silicon. Instead of dissipating the excess energy of above-bandgap photons as heat, impact ionisation generates multiple electron–hole pairs per absorbed photon. This mechanism directly enhances the photocurrent and reduces thermalisation losses, offering a fundamentally new route to surpass the efficiency limits of conventional Si-PV.

In contrast to tandem architectures or external conversion layers (based on photon up- or down-conversion), LEEM is fully compatible with crystalline silicon. It requires no additional absorber materials and relies on established industrial processes such as ion implantation, annealing and low-temperature metallisation. These features position LEEM as a scalable and cost-effective innovation pathway, building on the strengths of mature Si-PV manufacturing.

3.1 Fundamental Principle of Electron Multiplication

Electron multiplication in semiconductors is generally associated with impact ionisation [2], where a high-energy carrier generates a secondary electron–hole pair once its kinetic energy exceeds a threshold. In bulk silicon, the probability of such events is low due to rapid carrier thermalisation. By introducing nanostructured regions with controlled disorder and confinement, the LEEM approach modifies scattering dynamics and increases the probability of secondary pair generation before thermalisation occurs.

Figure 2: Theoretical comparison between impact ionisation, Multiple Exciton Generation (MEG) [3-5] and the LEEM mechanism. The staircase-like curves represent the stepwise increase in electrons per photon as photon energy rises. In the LEEM scenario, assuming a constant probability of secondary generation of 80%, the average carrier multiplication exceeds that of standard impact ionisation. Standard reference solar spectra AM0 and AM1.5G [6] are indicated in light green and light blue

respectively.

3.2 Nanostructuring by Ion Implantation

The enabling step of the LEEM concept is the controlled introduction of amorphised silicon (a-Si) nanolayers within a c-Si matrix. This is achieved by ion implantation at carefully selected energies and doses, followed by annealing. The process generates buried amorphised regions, which may be continuous or spatially modulated, acting as active sites for carrier multiplication. Subsequent annealing partially recrystallises the matrix, stabilising the nanostructures while preserving their electronic functionality.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) confirms the structural integration of these buried layers. Preliminary experiments at CEA-Leti have demonstrated discontinuous nanometre-scale layers without compromising the crystalline quality of the surrounding silicon. Such precise nanostructuring within standard wafers represents a key innovation of LEEMONS, leveraging microelectronics-derived implantation tools for photovoltaic applications.

3.3 Precision Implantation Using Hard Masks

Efficient LEEM layers require nanostructuring that supports electronic transport while enabling carrier multiplication. Electrical carriers must be able to cross the amorphised silicon regions through crystalline passages and the feature sizes must remain small since hot electrons in silicon thermalise extremely rapidly, within tens to a few hundred femtoseconds [7]. This ultrafast relaxation imposes strict constraints on the spatial scale of implanted features. To meet these requirements, LEEMONS employs hard masks for ion implantation. Two complementary approaches are being developed:

- Ultra-thin silicon masks, fabricated at UMLP using Deep Reactive Ion Etching (RIE). These masks, with $\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$ apertures, enable the definition of patterned implantation zones over large wafer areas.
- Metallic mesh masks, consisting of $\sim 7 \mu\text{m}$ -wide metallic wires assembled into large-area meshes. These masks are robust and compatible with industrial wafer sizes.

Compared to conventional photoresist patterning, hard masks avoid surface contamination and damage while enabling discontinuous implantation at scale. Early results demonstrate that such masks can generate buried amorphised layers with periodicity, enabling reproducible definition of electron multiplication zones.

3.4 Integration into Device Architectures

For LEEM technology to demonstrate its industrial impact, it must be integrated into the mainstream silicon solar cell designs that dominate current and emerging production. The project therefore focuses on three representative architectures:

- PERC (Passivated Emitter Rear Contact): long established as a leading industrial architecture, PERC continues to represent a very large share of global production. Its widespread adoption makes it a relevant platform for demonstrating the compatibility of LEEM layers with mass manufacturing.

- HJT (Heterojunction): offering excellent passivation quality and high open-circuit voltages, HJT is increasingly seen as a pathway to higher efficiency. LEEM layers must be integrated in a way that preserves the low-temperature processing conditions required by this architecture.
- IBC-HJT (Interdigitated Back Contact HJT): combining advanced metallisation with the benefits of heterojunction passivation, IBC-HJT represents one of the most promising high-end cell architectures. Demonstrating LEEM compatibility in this configuration paves the way toward next-generation devices.

Across all these device types, the key challenges are to minimise defect-induced recombination, maintain effective passivation and adapt metallisation strategies.

3.5 Metallisation and Passivation Challenges

Metallisation and passivation are critical bottlenecks for LEEM cell integration. Conventional high-temperature metallisation (>400 °C) risks modifying or erasing the implanted nanostructures. To address this, low-temperature alternatives are developed by ISC and Roltec to preserve the integrity of the LEEM layers while delivering high conductivity.

Passivation within the LEEM framework is approached as a coupled materials and process optimisation problem. Investigations consider alternative dielectric layers, modified deposition conditions and engineered interface treatments to accommodate the presence of ion-implanted nanostructures. Particular attention is given to how implantation, annealing and passivation steps interact, since process sequencing strongly influences both carrier lifetimes and structural stability.

Advances in metallisation and passivation are therefore central to validating the feasibility of LEEM integration. Establishing stable and reproducible processes in these areas will define the boundary conditions under which LEEM can be considered alongside other emerging concepts for high-efficiency silicon photovoltaics.

3.6 Advantages over Tandem and Other Novel Concepts

Several approaches are currently being investigated to overcome the efficiency limitations of single-junction silicon solar cells. Tandem devices combine absorbers with different bandgaps and have demonstrated high laboratory efficiencies, but they require the integration of heterogeneous materials, additional interconnection layers and significant modifications to production infrastructure. Photon conversion layers, which aim to modify the incident spectrum through up- or down-conversion processes, remain limited by incomplete conversion efficiencies and coupling losses. Hot-carrier solar cells represent another direction of research, although their practical implementation is hindered by the lack of absorber materials capable of sustaining slow carrier cooling.

The LEEM concept differs from these strategies by altering the response of silicon itself. Ion implantation and thermal treatments create nanostructured regions that enhance impact ionisation and allow multiple charge

carriers to be generated from a single high-energy photon. This approach does not rely on supplementary absorbers or external spectral modification, but instead employs processes already established in the semiconductor and photovoltaic industries.

From a manufacturing perspective, this compatibility with existing equipment and process flows is a central advantage. LEEM offers the possibility of enhancing photocurrent generation while maintaining continuity with established crystalline silicon technology, thereby extending the scope of efficiency improvements within a familiar industrial framework.

4 PROGRESS AND RESULTS

4.1 Nanostructured Layer Fabrication

During the first year of the project, ion implantation experiments at CEA-Leti successfully produced discontinuous amorphised silicon layers embedded in crystalline silicon. However, the preliminary silicon masks used to create these discontinuities were not yet optimised. Their rough geometry generated extensive shadowing effects and limited the formation of buried discontinuous amorphised layers, making detection with standard ellipsometry techniques more challenging.

Therefore, complementary characterisation methods such as Raman spectroscopy, backscattered electron spectroscopy and TEM had to be employed to confirm the structural integration of the amorphised layers.

Figure 3: TEM image of an a-Si layer embedded into c-Si by ion implantation for LEEMONS project.

4.2 Hard Mask Development

UMLP developed ultra-thin silicon masks with 10 μm apertures using a deep-RIE process. These masks were successfully tested at CEA-Leti, marking the first validated milestone of the LEEMONS project. Early experiments in Grenoble demonstrated for the first time the feasibility of fabricating discontinuous buried amorphised layers using hard masks with 10 μm apertures.

In parallel, a second masking approach has been designed to enable smaller apertures (up to 7 μm) and thinner masks. This method adapts standard metallic stencil printing masks, which are modified and coated to prevent contamination and to operate inside an ion implantation chamber. Production of these metallic mesh masks began in September 2025 in Japan, followed by final assembly in Spain and specialised coating in France.

These hard masks enable discontinuous ion implantation without the need for photoresist deposition

and removal, thereby avoiding potential damage to wafers.

Figure 4: Ultra-thin mesh mask ($\sim 7\mu\text{m}$ stainless steel wires) that allows discontinuous ion implantation.

4.3 Low-Temperature Metallisation

At ISC Konstanz, several metallisation alternatives have been investigated to reduce thermal budgets and preserve the integrity of the implanted nanostructures. Initial lab-scale trials included contact resistance measurements across different metallisation pastes and temperature profiles, as well as mini-cell experiments using three test structures with varied diffusions. These experiments provided the first comparative data on how peak firing temperature influences performance.

In parallel, the amorphised nanostructure resistance tests were initiated in September 2025. SEGTON and CEA provided two implanted wafers that were subjected to optimised metallisation temperature curves. Ongoing characterisation will determine the maximum thermal budget that LEEMONS nanostructures can withstand.

Alternative metallisation routes are also under assessment. For example, LECO firing with adapted pastes is planned, although its compatibility with mini-Zebra architectures is still being evaluated due to the back-contact design. These exploratory trials aim to identify metallisation schemes that minimise process temperature while ensuring good electrical contact quality.

Roltec conducted multiple metal contact deposition trials and demonstrated the fabrication of electrodes with ohmic contact on silicon at process temperatures below $100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ using silver deposition by magnetron sputtering. This approach allows the formation of contacts for Zebra IBC solar cells under low-temperature metallisation conditions, thereby preserving the structural integrity of the LEEMONS nanostructures.

Figure 5: Measuring electrodes on an alternatively metallised sample prepared for LEEMONS.

4.4 Passivation optimisation tests on-going

The first integration steps have combined ion-implanted nanostructured layers with n-type crystalline silicon cells, marking the transition from material-level experiments to device-level validation. Passivation optimisation is currently ongoing at ISC Konstanz and CSEM, with multiple complementary approaches under investigation.

CEA-Leti's July 2025 implantation campaign provided wafers that are now being characterised and prepared for passivation at CSEM. Two diffusion routes are under evaluation: POCl_3 diffusion with etch-back and PECVD $\text{SiO}_x:\text{P}$ diffusion, both yielding promising profiles for front surface fields. CSEM has initiated lifetime studies to compare their effectiveness, with first results showing alignment with the LEEMONS concept.

Overall, the passivation optimisation campaign aims to balance effective suppression of recombination with seamless integration into the LEEMONS nanostructuring process, laying the foundation for functional PERC and HJT prototypes in the next phases.

5 IMPACT AND RELEVANCE

The LEEMONS concept addresses critical challenges in the PV industry:

- **Sustainability:** process relies on recyclable materials and minimises additional steps.
- **Industrial compatibility:** integration with existing PERC/HJT production lines avoids costly infrastructure changes.
- **EU policy alignment:** supports strategic autonomy and climate neutrality targets.

If successful, LEEMONS could extend the relevance of Si-PV, enabling higher efficiencies without the complexity of tandems and positioning Europe at the forefront of next-generation solar innovation.

6 CONCLUSIONS

LEEMONS introduces a fundamentally novel PV concept based on low-energy electron multiplication in nanostructured silicon. Initial progress validates ion implantation masks, amorphised layers and metallisation alternatives, laying the groundwork for full device integration. The upcoming project phases will focus on integrating LEEM layers into PERC and HJT prototypes, benchmarking performance and assessing scalability.

By coupling scientific innovation with industrial relevance, LEEMONS aims to deliver a disruptive, cost-effective pathway to higher Si-PV efficiency and long-term sustainability.

7 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101172870

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